

ISSUES OF IMPROVING ADMINISTRATIVE RESPONSIBILITY FOR TRAFFIC VIOLATIONS

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Abstract

Today, comprehensive practical measures for the prevention of road traffic accidents are being determined and implemented by our Government. In this regard, the article mentions impunity among young drivers who want to show their disrespect to other road users by deliberately and repeatedly violating the rules of the road, which clearly shows disrespect for society without ensuring the execution of several penalties established by drivers who commit regular traffic violations in the vehicle and "traffic hooliganism" which includes the creation of an environment of lack of control, as well as the fact that they put up obstacles consisting of several vehicles, organize a race with the incorrect use of sound signals, make dangerous movements (maneuvers) in traffic flows (for example, suddenly change the direction of movement) ", based on foreign experience and statistical analysis, the proposals for future administrative liability legislation are reflected.

Keywords: Legislation on traffic rules, vehicle, violation, dangerous driving of a vehicle, traffic disorder, administrative offense, administrative liability, administrative penalty, administrative responsibility, legal norm.

Building a legal democratic society with the rule of law in the Republic of Uzbekistan is defined as the highest goal. Article 15 of the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan states that "the supremacy of the Constitution and laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall be unconditionally recognized in the Republic of Uzbekistan. "Citizens are obliged to comply with the Constitution and laws, to respect the rights, freedoms, honor and dignity of other people" is a clear proof of this.

However, if we study the extent to which our citizens comply with our current laws today, at the video selector meeting held on February 11 of this year under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev,

he spoke about the existing problems and shortcomings in the field of road safety and said that "road safety is the most important issue today. that it is an important and urgent issue, more than 10,000 accidents occurred in our country in 2021, in which more than 9,000 citizens were injured, and it is a great tragedy that about 2,500 people, including 263 children, died" [1], emphasizing The Prime Minister of the Republic of Uzbekistan and heads of all ministries and state bodies, regional governors, as well as the leadership of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the leaders of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Communications of the Republic of Uzbekistan expressed their objection.

Indeed, at the core of the reforms implemented in the field of road safety today, "man and his life lie", but as the President noted above, we are not without shortcomings.

The issue of the citizens of our republic and their lives comes to mind when the President calls it a "big tragedy".

There are certainly both objective and subjective reasons for such tragedies.

Ушбу видеоселектор йиғилишида Президентимиз томонидан таъкидланган статистик рақамлар ва сабаблардан айримларига эътибор қаратадиган бўлсак, фуқароларнинг йўл ҳаракати қоидабузарликларини мунтазам равишда такроран содир этганлигини кўришимиз мумкин. Жумладан, Президентимиз "Юнусобод туманида яшовчи ҳайдовчи 2021 йилда 133 маротаба қоидабузарлик содир этганлиги (230 миллион сўм жарима ҳисобланган), Юқоричирчиқ туманида яшовчи ҳайдовчи 2021 йил 11 ойида 37 маротаба қоидабузарлик содир қилиб, охир-оқибат жиддий авария содир этган" дея, таъкидлади.

If we pay attention to some of the statistical figures and reasons highlighted by the President in this video selector meeting, we can see that citizens regularly commit traffic violations. In particular, the President said, "A driver living in Yunusabad district committed 133 violations in 2021 (a fine of 230 million soums was calculated), the driver living in Yukorichirchik district committed 37 violations in 11 months of 2021 and eventually caused a serious accident," he said.

According to the statistical data highlighted by the President, the main reasons for these violations are lack of respect for the current laws of our republic, lack of knowledge of the laws, or other reasons of some drivers.

In particular, "...when critically analyzing the unfortunate situations in the field based on statistical data, 45% of road traffic accidents are caused by

disregarding the rules by drivers, 10% by inexperience of drivers, 25% by road conditions and infrastructure that do not meet the requirements, and 20% by pedestrians not following the rules"[3] as it is.

When analyzing some of the above-mentioned statistics, for example, 45 percent of the more than 10,000 road traffic accidents committed in 2021 were caused by the disregard of the rules by drivers.

It is 4.5 thousand, and if we divide the total number of deaths of 2.5 thousand people into 45 percent of the number of drivers who ignore the rules, we understand that 1125 people lost their lives prematurely due to this reason.

As can be seen from the above, these statistics show an undeniable unpleasant reality.

At the meeting, President Sh.M.Mirziyoev highlighted the existing shortcomings in the field and put forward a number of proposals for its improvement and modernization. . Due to the increased number of cases of serious violations and their repetition, ensuring the inevitability of punishment, especially the introduction of a new type of responsibility called "traffic disorder", especially for driving a car in a disorderly manner and interfering with other drivers, has set a number of clear priority tasks.

Of course, responsibility is inevitable and punishment for an existing deed, so today's processes of globalization certainly do not fail to have an impact on the way of life and morals of people.

In particular, as a result of the flow of information, we are facing ideas that are contrary to our mentality and values. "Popular culture" has a negative impact on our art, dress culture, and education. Globalization processes accelerate popular culture. Under this guise, spreading the ideas of immorality, obscenity, violence, disrespecting and disrespecting the national traditions and values of other peoples that have been cherished for centuries, and threats aimed at their destruction will not fail to cause concern for any person with no spirituality.

Today, considering immorality, uncivilization, lack of spirituality as freedom, disregarding national traditions and values, considering them as old fashioned, poses a great threat to spiritual life, sanctity of family and education of youth.

Some of our young people who are growing up in this worldview have become a habit of disrespecting the rules, engaging in anti-social behavior, and committing actions such as "traffic hooliganism", which is considered an illegal act.

In our current laws, there is responsibility for illegal acts such as "hooliganism", "petty hooliganism", researches have been conducted by scientists to determine the signs, symptoms and methods of committing these acts, causes and

conditions, and they have given relevant legal conclusions and recommendations in this regard.

Today, regarding the classification of the concept of "traffic hooliganism", Russian legal scholars I.M. and Likhachev N.A. researches are carried out and explain the essence of the concept of "traffic hooliganism" by the behavior manifested in "dangerous driving" of the vehicle as follows: deliberate sudden acceleration by the driver at the start of the movement of the vehicle, sudden braking, side and his own classifies as actions related to sudden change of the direction of movement without ensuring the distance in the directions of movement, without turning on the maneuvering signs, making noises that disturb the peace of citizens [4].

These scientists studied the legislation of Great Britain, the Netherlands and Sweden on determining responsibility for these actions. as the index is calculated. The reason for this is the amount of fines set for "dangerous driving" of a vehicle compared to other European countries in the legislation of these countries.

For example, the road traffic act adopted in Great Britain in 1956 even provides for criminal responsibility for "dangerous driving", as well as norms limiting the power of the vehicle for young drivers who have the right to drive a vehicle. available[5].

The law adopted in 1960 as a supplement to the road traffic act and as an auxiliary law to this law established a criminal penalty of five years imprisonment for causing death due to "dangerous driving" of a vehicle. Because when qualified according to their legislation, speeding while driving a vehicle without objective and correct assessment of the situation, endangering other people and drivers, is considered as speeding [6].

This approach in the legislation of these countries is from the last century In the 1970s, especially in Great Britain, pedestrian fatalities were associated with an increase in road traffic accidents, and over the past 40 years, this situation has increased by 78%, road traffic accidents involving human deaths by 7%, "dangerous" driving accidents by drivers in vehicles. management" decreased by 16%[7].

Foreign experience shows that, according to their legislation, the law prevails only if society and the state are intolerant of "dangerous driving" of the vehicle, which includes the actions classified above.

Also scientists Hill I.M. and Likhachev N.A., in the opinion of N.A., society and the state should be uncompromising in combating traffic violations manifested in

"dangerous driving" of a vehicle, and several cases should be taken into account when imposing a heavier punishment.

First, recognizing the vehicle as a vehicle of high risk, the driver should be proportionately responsible for driving it during "dangerous driving", because at that time he should have assessed his actions as a socially dangerous act and should have foreseen that he would have socially dangerous consequences.

Also, given that the driver knows the traffic rules and strictly follows them, it can be said that he committed the violation of these rules intentionally (indirectly or directly).

In recent times, there has been an increase in cases of deliberate and repeated violations of traffic rules, which clearly show disrespect for society.

One of the main reasons for such behavior is the emergence of an atmosphere of impunity and lack of control among young drivers who want to show their disrespect to other road users, as well as by them setting up barriers of several vehicles, organizing races by misusing sound signals, such as making dangerous movements (maneuvers) in traffic flows (for example, suddenly changing the direction of movement).

In order to legally classify the concept of "traffic disorder", we need to focus on some drivers who drive a vehicle in our daily life. In particular, they have been subject to an administrative penalty for two or more violations of the traffic rules, or have not paid a fine for several administrative penalties, and continue to commit such offenses without paying the fine, preventing a traffic accident, human life in the course of traffic. and causing dangerous situations for health, without preventing damage to vehicles, structures, loads and other material damage, intentionally accelerating the vehicle, sudden braking, without ensuring the distance in the side and own directions of movement, without turning on the maneuvering signs changing, or exiting to the side or lane intended for oncoming traffic in violation of traffic rules, caused the occurrence of an accident, i.e. caused other road users to change speed, direction of movement sharply or at their own risk We are witnessing actions that force people to take other measures to ensure the safety of others or other citizens, as well as taking out a body part in a vehicle with deliberate disregard for public order, and making noises that disturb the peace of others.

Based on the above comments and analysis, if it is concluded that punishment must be ensured for such actions, then the structure of the legal norm that provides responsibility based on the current legislation on administrative

responsibility, as well as what are included in the actions that are legally described in the disposition of the norm that makes up its content.

In our opinion, it is appropriate to supplement the Code of Administrative Responsibility of the Republic of Uzbekistan with a new version of the article that stipulates responsibility for these actions,

"... Article. Bullying on the road"

"Hooliganism on the road, i.e. non-observance of the intermediate distance by the driver of the motor vehicle, the start of the movement with sudden acceleration of the vehicle, sudden braking, which creates dangerous situations for human life and health as a result of such acceleration or braking, as well as committing actions related to causing damage to structures, loads and other material damages".

References:

1. [1,2,3]<https://yuz.uz/news/yol-harakati-xavfsizligini-kuchaytirish-choralari-muhokama-qilindi> 2022 yil February 11
2. [4,5,6]<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/aktualnye-aspekty-protivodeystviya-agressivnomu-vozhdeniyu-i-dorozhnomu-huliganstvu-v-rossiyskoy-federatsii>
3. [7] Potapenkova I.V. On the establishment of administrative responsibility for dangerous (aggressive) driving in the Russian Federation and law enforcement practice of attracting drivers for dangerous driving in the United Kingdom of Great Britain and Northern Ireland: analysis and possibility of use // Perfection of legislation on police and police activity. 2016.

